

AI Sustainability in Practice

Part Two: Sustainability Throughout the AI Workflow

What is the AI Ethics and Governance in Practice Programme?

In 2021, the UK's National AI Strategy recommended that UK Government's official Public Sector Guidance on AI Ethics and Safety be transformed into a series of practice-based workbooks. The result is the AI Ethics and Governance in Practice Programme. This series of eight workbooks provides end-to-end guidance on how to apply principles of AI ethics and safety to the design, development, deployment, and maintenance of AI systems. It provides public sector organisations with a Process-Based Governance (PBG) Framework designed to assist AI project teams in ensuring that the AI technologies they build, procure, or use are ethical, safe, and responsible.

At a Glance

- Explores how to put the **SUM Values** and the principle of **AI Sustainability** into practice throughout the AI design, development, and deployment lifecycle.
- Discusses **Stakeholder Impact Assessments (SIAs)** in depth, providing tools and training resources to help AI project teams conduct these. This includes:
 - providing a template of the **SIA** and activities that allow a deeper dive into crucial parts of it;
 - discussing methods for weighing values and considering trade-offs during the **SIA**; and
 - highlighting the need to treat the **SIA** as an end-to-end process of responsive evaluation and re-assessment.

Key Concepts

AI Sustainability

The principle of AI Sustainability ensures that designers and users of AI systems remain aware that these technologies may have transformative effects as well as short-, medium-, and long-term impacts on individuals and society. For AI systems to remain sustainable and support the sustainability of affected communities, AI project teams should proceed with a continuous sensitivity to such real-world effects and impacts.

Stakeholders

Stakeholders are individuals or groups that:

1. have interests or rights that may be affected by the past, present, and future decisions and activities of an organisation;
2. may have the power or authority to influence the outcome of such decisions and activities; and/or
3. have relevant characteristics that put them in positions of advantage or vulnerability with regard to those decisions and activities.

SUM Values

A set of ethical values that provide AI project teams with a shared vocabulary to assess the ethical implications of AI projects and to support, underwrite and motivate responsible innovation practice. Rather than providing comprehensive list, they are meant to be a launching point for collaborative and anticipatory reflection, allowing for the respectful and interculturally sensitive inclusion of other points of view.

Stakeholder Impact Assessment

SIAs are tools that create a procedure for, and a means of documenting, the collaborative evaluation and reflective anticipation of the possible harms and benefits of AI innovation projects. But, these are not just one-off governance actions. SIAs must pay continuous attention both to the dynamic and changing character of AI production and implementation lifecycles and to the shifting conditions of the real-world environments in which AI technologies are embedded.

Workbook Summary

The sustainability of AI systems depends on the capacity of project teams to proceed with a continuous sensitivity to their potential real-world impacts and transformative effects. Stakeholder Impact Assessments (SIAs) are governance mechanisms that enable this kind of responsiveness. They are tools that create a procedure for, and a means of documenting, the collaborative evaluation and reflective

anticipation of the possible harms and benefits of AI innovation projects. SIAs are not one-off governance actions. They require project teams to pay continuous attention to the dynamic and changing character of AI production and use and to the shifting conditions of the real-world environments in which AI technologies are embedded. This workbook is part two of two workbooks on AI Sustainability. It provides a template of the SIA and activities that allow a deeper dive into crucial parts of it. It discusses methods for weighing values and considering trade-offs during the SIA. And, it highlights the need to treat the SIA as an end-to-end process of responsive evaluation and re-assessment.

Stakeholder Impact Assessment (Sample Questions)

SECTION 1: Design Phase

Horizon-Scanning and the Decision to Design

- a. Is building an AI model or tool the right solution?
- b. Has human rights compliance across the supply chain been checked?

Goal-Setting and Objective-Mapping

- a. Is the definition of the outcome that the system is optimising for fair, reasonable, and widely acceptable?
- b. Have impacted communities been involved in this definition?

Possible Impacts on the Individual

- a. How, if at all, might the use of the AI system enhance or diminish the autonomy of impacted people?
- b. How might it do harm to their physical, mental, or moral integrity?

Possible Impacts on Society

- a. How, if at all, might the use of the system affect the integrity of meaningful human connection, and social cohesion?
- b. How, if at all, might its use affect freedom of assembly and association?

SECTION 2: Development Phase

- a. Are the trained model's actual objective, design, and testing results still in line with the evaluations and conclusions contained in your original assessment?
- b. Have any other areas of concern arisen with regard to possibly harmful social or ethical impacts as you have moved from the design to the development phase?

SECTION 3: Deployment Phase

- a. How does the content of the existing SIA compare with the real-world impacts of the AI system as measured by available evidence of performance, monitoring data, and input from implementers and the public?
- b. Have any unintended harmful consequences ensued in the wake of the deployment of the system?

Sustainability Throughout the AI Lifecycle

Sustainable AI design, development, and use must remain agile, attentive to change, and at-the-ready to move back and forth across the decision-making pipeline as downstream actions affect upstream choices and evaluations. There are two factors that necessitate this demand for agility and responsiveness in sustainable AI innovation:

1. Production and Implementation Factors

Choices made at any point along the AI workflow may impact prior decisions and assessments. This leads to a need for re-assessment, reconsideration, and amendment. For instance, design and development choices could be made that were not anticipated in the initial impact assessment. Such choices might include adjusting the target variable, choosing a more complex algorithm, or grouping variables in ways that impact specific groups. Changes may influence how an AI system performs or how it impacts affected individuals and groups. Processes of AI design, development, and use are also iterative and frequently bi-directional. This often results in the need for revision and update.

2. Environmental Factors

During the time in which the system is in production or use, changes in project-relevant social, regulatory, policy or legal environments may occur. These changes may have a bearing on how well the system works and on how the deployment of the system impacts affected individuals and groups. Likewise, domain-level reforms, policy changes, or changes in data recording methods may take place in the population of concern. This could affect whether the data used to train the model accurately portrays phenomena, populations, or related factors in an accurate manner. In the same vein, cultural or behavioural shifts may occur within affected populations that alter the underlying data distribution. This can hamper the performance of a model, which has been trained on data collected prior to such shifts.

For detailed information about authorships, acknowledgements, and references, please consult the **AI Sustainability in Practice Part Two: Sustainability Throughout the AI Workflow** workbook.